

Terpenoids Part LXXXIII : Synthesis of a Stereoisomer of dl-Hotrienol

O. P. VIG, BHAGAT RAM, URMIL RANI and JATINDER KAUR

Department of Chemistry, Punjab University, Chandigarh-160014,

Manuscript received 17 October 1973; accepted 13 March 1974

Synthesis of a stereoisomer of dl-Hotrienol has been accomplished through the dehydration of an appropriate secondary allylic-alcohol with $\text{POCl}_3\text{-Py}$. under mild conditions.

HOTRIENOL, a mono terpene *tert*-alcohol, obtained from Japanese Ho-leaf oil¹ has been assigned the constitution (I) on the basis of spectroscopic and chemical studies.

Vig *et al.* recently reported the synthesis² of this *tert*-alcohol (I), in which the 2, 4-disubstituted diene system has been created through the Wittig reaction of a suitably substituted aldehyde with β -methallylidetriphenylphosphorane. The present communication, however, reports another synthesis of dl-hotrienol in which the characteristic diene system has been generated through the dehydration of the corresponding secondary allylic alcohol under mild conditions. The synthetic compound, however differed from the natural hotrienol as it showed no absorption in the 960-970 cm^{-1} region in its infrared spectrum thus indicating the presence of the *cis* geometry around the $\text{C}_5\text{-C}_6$ double bond.

The scheme of reaction is depicted in Chart (I)

CHART :- I

The starting compound (II), obtained exactly according to the procedure already reported,³ was

a thin liquid film. The microanalyses were done by Mr. L. K. Khullar.

2-Methyl-6, 6-ethylenedioxy-1, 3-heptadiene (III) :

Phosphorous oxychloride (9 ml.) was added dropwise to a well stirred solution of the allylic alcohol (II, 9g.) in anhydrous pyridine (66 ml) kept at 0°. The contents were stirred for 2 hrs at the same temperature and left over night. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual. The solvent was expelled and the residual oil was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina, eluting with petroleum ether to afford ketal-diene (III, 5g) in 61 per cent yield, η_D^{21} 1.4780; (Found : C, 71.15; H, 9.40. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 71.43; H, 9.52%) ν_{max} 3070, 2950, 1645, 1610, 1450, 1375, 1260, 1230, 1145, 1065, 895, 870 and 760 cm^{-1} .

6-Methyl-4, 6-heptadien-2-one (IV) :

To the ketal-diene (III, 3g.) was added acetone (70 ml), *p*-toluene sulphonic acid (1.3g.) and water (9 ml.) and the reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1 hr. The excess of *p*-toluene sulphonic acid was removed with 5 per cent sodium carbonate solution and worked up in the usual manner. After removal of the solvent, the residue was distilled under reduced pressure to furnish keto-diene (IV, 1.5g.) in 68 per cent yield, b.p. 105°/6 mm, η_D^{21} 1.4820. (Found : C, 77.20; H, 9.30. $C_8H_{12}O$ requires C, 77.42; H, 9.68%) ν_{max} 3070, 2900, 1720, 1650, 1610, 1460, 1370, 1260, 1160, 1095, 995, 900 and 770 cm^{-1} .

3, 7-Dimethyl-3-hydroxy-1, 5, 7-octatriene (I) (Stereoisomer of *dl*-Hotrienol) :

Grignard reagent was prepared from magnesium (0.47g) and vinyl bromide (2g.) in anhydrous tetrahydrofuran (60 ml). To this was added dropwise

keto-diene (IV; 1.0g) in dry THF (15 ml) with stirring and left overnight. The contents were refluxed for 1 hr and thereafter worked up in the usual way. The solvent was removed and the residue was distilled under reduced pressure. The product was further purified by chromatography over neutral alumina, elution with dry ether giving 3, 7-dimethyl-3-hydroxy-1, 5, 7-octatriene (I, 0.8g) in 65 per cent yield; b.p. 115°/6 mm; η_D^{21} 1.4900. (Found : C, 78.59; H, 10.50. $C_{10}H_{16}O$ requires C, 78.95; H, 10.53%). \int_{max} 3560, 3075, 1650, 1615, 1450, 1380, 1115, 1000, 925, 890 and 745 cm^{-1} . The spectrum is comparable to that of the natural sample¹ of hotrienol except in the region 960-970 cm^{-1} in its infrared spectrum. The natural sample shows a peak at 971 cm^{-1} while there is no corresponding absorption in the synthetic sample. This indicates the presence of a *cis*-isomer.

UV Spectrum $\lambda_{max}^{ethanol} = 225$ nm. Lit.¹ reports for *trans* hotrienol

$$\lambda_{max}^{ethanol} = 230 \text{ nm}$$

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (J. K.) is grateful to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, for the award of a junior research fellowship.

References

1. T. YOSHIDA, S. MURAKI, H. KAWAMURA and A. KOMATSU, *Agr. Biol. Chem.*, 1965, **33**, 343.
2. O. P. VIG, J. CHANDER and B. RAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 793.
3. O. P. VIG., J. C. KAPOOR, (MISS.) C. K. KHURANA and B. VIG, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 505.